

A New Stage of Youth Policy in Uzbekistan: Innovative Technologies in Higher Education

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Abstract. *This article examines the state policy towards youth in our country and the regulatory documents adopted to bring it to a new level, the main tasks and achievements within the framework of these tasks defined in them. The most important achievements and modernization of educational processes, training of specialists in accordance with world requirements, reform and improvement of the education system, and introduction of innovative technologies are revealed in detail.*

Key words: *public policy, modernization, educational process, social activity, innovative methods, new pedagogical technologies, improvement of the education system, mass culture.*

The future of every society is determined by the level of development of the education system, which is an integral part of it and a vital necessity. Today, reforming and improving the continuous education system of our country, which is on the path of independent development, raising it to a new level of quality, introducing innovative technologies into it, and increasing the efficiency of education have been raised to the level of state policy.

Future development depends on the intellectual thinking, knowledge experience and professional training of today's young generation. Helping young people to find their place in life, to freely express their potential, and to provide them with work has always been in the attention of our state. The development of every country, its future and its power depend primarily on the extent to which the young people of that country are educated, ambitious, patriotic and responsible. The speed and abundance of information that has appeared in the current globalization period, and the diversity of its distribution ways, also demands that young people acquire such characteristics as independent worldview, critical thinking, social activity, self-awareness and responsibility for the country's destiny.

Therefore, globalization itself requires rapid movement, immediate acquisition of necessary information, their processing and effective implementation.

In the first years of our independence, our First President put forward the idea that "Our children must be stronger, more educated, wiser and certainly happier than us." It was through this thought that our president determined that education of a well-rounded person is one of the priority directions of Uzbekistan's policy. In fact, young people who are mature, who have a deep knowledge of their profession and specialty, who can fully respond to modern requirements and who can feel the unity of the country's destiny with their own destiny, who understand their relevance to all the realities happening in our country and act accordingly, are the ground that will provide our future.

In Uzbekistan, youth policy has become the most important part of state policy. This is clearly confirmed by the fact that more than three hundred legal documents on youth were adopted by our country during the period of independence and are consistently implemented.

For example, on September 14, 2016, the Laws "On the State Policy of Uzbekistan regarding youth" and on January 25, 2022 "On the introduction of amendments to certain legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan in connection with the improvement of the system of work with youth" were adopted.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 5, 2017 "On improving the effectiveness of state youth policy and supporting the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan" and dated June 30, 2020 "On measures to radically reform the state policy regarding youth in the Republic of Uzbekistan and bring it to a new level" decrees were accepted. At the same time, on August 12, 2022, the decisions of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to expand opportunities for modern knowledge and professional acquisition", "On measures to bring the field of information and communication technologies to a new level in 2022-2023" The decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers dated June 7, 2022 "On approval of the program of implementation of the state policy on youth in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2023" were adopted.

To the Youth Union of Uzbekistan in 2022-2023, reforms within the framework of the implementation program of the state policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan on youth "consist of complex measures aimed at acquiring knowledge and skills, creating decent working and living conditions for them, and meaningful organization of free time" [1] a number of new and important tasks related to increasing youth activity were defined.

"On the measures of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to fundamentally reform and advance the state policy on youth in Uzbekistan to a new level, to develop effective solutions to problems in the field of youth, to effectively organize and coordinate the activities of competent bodies" The Youth Affairs Agency under the Ministry of Youth Policy and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established by decree.

In the implementation of the state policy on youth in our republic, the Youth Affairs Agency was determined to be an organization that "educates young people in the spirit of loyalty to the Motherland, respect for national and universal values, protects them from information that harms their health, and widely involves the growing young generation in science and innovation.

At the same time, the agency will become a professional activity organization that unites young people around the idea of "From national revival to national rise".

According to this decree, "The director of the State Service Development Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan is an initiator of the formation of a pool of promising personnel among young people, an active participant in the implementation of reforms and solving local problems, and the introduction of the institutional system "Pride of the Motherland" that supports young people worthy of leadership positions task" [2] was defined.

Especially, the fact that the rights and interests of the young generation are sealed with specific articles in our updated Constitution, without a doubt, makes it possible to further expand the legal base in this regard and raise our practical work to a new level.

This puts the task of raising the level of the state policy of the development of the education system to higher education in our country, and mobilizing all the forces and opportunities so that young people can acquire modern knowledge and professions in conditions corresponding to world standards.

Therefore, the modernization of educational processes should be the main professional problem of today's teacher in order to prepare specialists who meet the world's requirements, to teach them and to be able to follow the learner.

In this regard, the Decree No. PF-6097 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 29, 2020 "On approval of the concept of development of science until 2030" was adopted. The concept defined the strategic goals, priorities, tasks, medium- and long-term stages of the development of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan and became the basis for the development of programs and complex measures related to the field.

Also, in the concept, expansion of coverage with higher education, improvement of the quality of training of highly educated specialists, introduction of digital technologies and modern methods into the educational process were defined as the priority directions of the development of the higher education system.

In order to fulfill these priority tasks, more than 30 branches of universities and institutes of countries such as South Korea, Great Britain, Russia, India, Italy, Singapore, and Latvia are operating in our country. In addition, 26[3] departments of the republic's higher educational institutions established in the regions are working.

Today, the number of higher education institutions has increased three times to 210, and the coverage level has increased from 9% to 38%, opening up new opportunities for our boys and girls in acquiring modern science and professions. In the last three years, over 6 trillion soums of preferential loans were allocated to 250,000 young people[3].

"Many new kindergartens, schools and universities are being built in our country. The material and technical base of educational and scientific institutions, personnel capacity is being strengthened. A new generation of textbooks and study guides is being created. Appreciating and encouraging the hard work of industry employees has been in the center of our constant attention. In the last seven years, we have increased the coverage level of pre-school education from 27% to 72%, higher education from 9% to 42%, and the number of our universities from 77 to 212, which is undoubtedly our most important achievement[4].

All opportunities have been created by our state to prepare young people who can meet the requirements of the time, who have all-round knowledge and professional skills, skills and qualifications, who are able to independently organize their lives, and who can effectively influence the development of the economy of our country. The purpose of this is to help every young person realize their dreams and take their place in society.

Therefore, one of the tasks of higher education is to provide high-level education and train qualified personnel based on modern educational programs.

Therefore, at present, the following requirements are imposed on the teaching process in higher education in Uzbekistan:

- quality, that is, obtaining the specified level of training;
- mass, i.e. a large number of students should acquire the specified level of education at the same time;
- efficiency, i.e. the expenses spent on training should definitely give the maximum effect.

Solving these tasks leads to the technologicalization of the teaching process, the development and implementation of innovative teaching technologies. It is important to increase the intellectual potential of teachers, to introduce them to new, innovative forms, methods and tools of teaching, to familiarize them with the qualities of professional competence and the essence of creative ability in pedagogues.

In the higher education system, the technology that makes the teacher and the student interested in working on themselves, activates and accelerates their actions is considered innovative teaching technologies.

Innovative teaching technologies are an orderly set of the most optimal ways and means of teaching, communication, information and management, which ensure the implementation of the educational goal and the guaranteed achievement of the expected results in the existing conditions and at the set time.

Innovative teaching technologies mean bringing innovations and changes to the educational system, pedagogical process, and the activity of the teacher and student, and innovative methods are used in the implementation of this process. Application of innovative methods in teaching is the teaching process

the most optimal way to achieve educational goals based on a technological approach is a pedagogical direction that explores the methods and tools, reveals the laws, and educational goals can be achieved based on a technological approach to the teaching process.

In higher education, pedagogues create the conditions to be aware of the organizational, technical and didactic possibilities of modern innovative educational technologies, to use innovative technologies of teaching in educational practice, to consistently develop the qualities of competence and creativity. At the same time, it ensures the strengthening of their skills in their effective use in professional activities.

This, in turn, is important in ensuring students' activities in the teaching process, improving the quality of education, and increasing efficiency.

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